

RESTORATION AND PRESERVATION OF THE TINCHOB MOSQUE IN THE CITY OF TASHKENT

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the restoration of the architectural monument — the Tinchob Mosque (1878), located in the Almazar District of Tashkent at the address: Sagbon Street, 1st Dead End, House 91. The building has survived to the present day, although some facades and individual structures have been reconstructed using modern materials. Currently, it is adapted and used as a neighborhood mosque.*

The purpose of the study is to develop a scientifically grounded restoration project that preserves the historical and architectural value of the building while restoring its original appearance. The work was carried out in accordance with the generally accepted methodology of scientific examination and architectural monument restoration design.

The research was conducted in three stages:

I -historical-archival and bibliographic studies;

II — field surveys using modern technologies, including laser scanning;

III — development of a preliminary restoration design.

The results of the study demonstrate the effectiveness of an integrated approach that combines traditional and innovative restoration methods aimed at preserving the cultural heritage of Tashkent.

Keywords: *restoration, architectural heritage, Tinchob Mosque, Tashkent, laser scanning, conservation, historical monuments.*

Introduction

The Tinchob Mosque was built in 1867, near the city center Chorsu in the Sebzar district. The completion of construction is confirmed by an inscription in Arabic calligraphy on the ceiling of the terrace, indicating the year 1290 AH (1878 CE).

In the 19th century, Tashkent was a large city surrounded by a fortress wall with twelve gates and a radial street layout radiating from its center Chorsu. In the mahallas, dense residential development was maintained, with narrow, winding streets and numerous cul-de-sacs. Elements of this old-city layout have partially survived to this day, although facades and individual buildings have been reconstructed using modern materials.

In the archives of the Cultural Heritage Agency, under No. 6312 (1954), there is a manuscript by art historian I. F. Borodina titled “*Diary of the Survey of Architectural Monuments of Tashkent.*” The document provides information about the condition of the Tinchob neighborhood mosque, built in the late 19th century.

According to Borodina, during the postwar period, the mosque building was adapted for use as a children’s consultation center, as a result of which the terrace was divided by partitions and the original layout was partially lost. The structure was framed building on a high base made

of fired brick with a metal roof. The ceilings and columns have preserved their original decorative paintings.

The mosque occupies the northwestern corner of the plot at the intersection of the streets of the Tinchob mahalla; its western wall faces toward Mecca. During the Soviet period, additional rooms were attached to the building, significantly altering its exterior appearance, which now resembles a residential house.

“*Folk Traditions of Uzbek Architecture*” (Moscow, 1951, p. 53), V. L. Voronina distinguishes three types of mosques: **namazgoh** for festive citywide prayers; **juma mosques** — for Friday services; and **neighborhood (guzar) mosques** — for the daily prayers of mahalla residents. The latter belong to the folk branch of architecture and structurally close to residential buildings: walls made of adobe or wooden frames, beam ceilings, and in cities sometimes domed roofs.

The Tinchob Mosque belongs to the third type — the neighborhood mosques, which characterized by compositional simplicity. Their structure typically combines a closed winter hall and an terrace describe as an open summer area whose form and layout depend on the configuration and size of the plot.

The plan of the Tinchob Mosque is unique and has no direct analogues. The closed part of the building stretches from west to east and is covered by a ceiling supported by two columns. To the south adjoins the iwan, oriented from north to south and rely on six columns, with a seventh column holding a small canopy at the eastern edge of the southern wall. The terrace was originally open on southern and eastern sides.

During the postwar period, the mosque was converted into a children’s clinic: the terrace was divided by septum and corridor was built between it in the main hall. Only the painted ceilings and some of the columns have survived from the original décor.

1.1 Report on the Results of Measurement Studies

The on-site measurements of the Tinchob Mosque were carried out using a high-precision **Ray II laser 3D scanner**, which features an extended range and allows for rapid capturing of large objects or scenes at distances of up to **130 meters**. The three-dimensional accuracy of the device meets professional standards and ensures **high angular precision** in measurements.

Figure 1

In the diagram (Figure 1), the **scanner installation points** are indicated, ensuring complete three-dimensional scanning of all buildings and the surrounding territory of the mosque.

Based on the obtained **point cloud**, a **3D model** of the structure was created, allowing for precise determination of its geometric parameters. The scanning results made it possible to generate **architectural drawings** — including plans, façades, and sections — as well as to produce **any horizontal and vertical cross-sections** of the building and its structural elements. Additionally, the collected data enable the development of **detailed interior drawings** and **3D models** of individual decorative components.

1.2 Report on Probes, Test Pits, and Openings

During the survey, **natural damage to the plaster layer** was identified in the **southeastern corner** of the enclosed (winter) hall, which was used as **Probe No. 1 (Figures 2–3)**. The probe confirmed the **timber-frame wall construction** previously noted by **I. F. Borodina**. The wooden structural elements were found to be in **satisfactory condition**, and the wall thickness—approximately **70 cm**—indicates a **double-frame system**. Layers of the **original clay–straw plaster** were discovered, overlaid with a **decorative ganch layer** and several **subsequent repair coatings**.

Figure 2

Figure 3

At present, the mosque is partially obscured by later additions. A visual inspection revealed that its **spatial and planning structure** has largely retained its **original form**. The building consists of an **enclosed winter hall** and an **open terrace**, complemented by a **small entrance canopy**.

The **ceilings** are constructed using a **traditional post-and-beam system**, forming **square coffers** with **vassal infill**. The **ceilings** are decorated with **polychrome paintings**, which, when compared to the descriptions by **I. F. Borodina (1954)**, have been **well preserved** to this day.

Figure 4 presents the **reconstruction scheme of the Tinchob Mosque plan**, where the **red dots** mark the **preserved original columns**. The analysis indicates that the surviving columns remain in **good structural condition** and **retain their load-bearing function**. However, **some columns have been lost**, and their role in the **spatial and structural system** of the building is now **performed by later repair walls and partitions** erected during subsequent modifications.

Figure 4

2. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE RESTORATION PROJECT

Based on the historical, archival, bibliographical, and on-site research conducted at the Tinchob Mosque in Tashkent. Also, taking into account its satisfactory state of preservation, it is recommended to restore the original architectural appearance of the monument.

The **restoration project** should focus on the **exposure, strengthening, and conservation** of the **preserved structural and decorative elements**, as well as on the **scientifically grounded reconstruction** of the **lost architectural components** of the building.

2.1 Structural Work

- the ground level have to be lower in the adjacent area to the historical elevation.
- Remove repair coverings: metal roofing, plank floors, partitions, and extensions.
- Restore lost columns using surviving examples.
- Strengthen and preserve the original walls, restoring damaged sections and opening up blocked-up openings.
 - Strengthen the wooden floor, reconstruct repaired sections, and restore lost elements in a manner similar to the original.

2.2 Architectural and Decorative Work

- Install a flat roof using modern thermal and waterproofing materials, with a traditional clay adobe render.
 - Restore parapets made of fired brick similar to the historical ones.
 - Carefully remove repair layers of plaster, preserving the original clay adobe finish; preserve and strengthen with a traditional mortar with modern additives.
 - Restore the plaster and stucco decoration based on the surviving model.
 - Install ganch lattices and wooden door and window frames in the traditional late 19th-century style.
 - Remove repair layers from the baked brick plinth, restore the joints, and apply strengthening compounds.

- Conserve the surviving ceiling paintings and partially restore lost sections in a manner reminiscent of the original.

2.3 Landscaping

- Develop a landscaping plan for the courtyard space, taking into account the historical plans.
- Provide for the construction of auxiliary facilities: a ablution room, toilet, pantry, kitchen, and teahouse.
- Provide the complex with the necessary utilities.

The implementation of these measures will recreate the historical and architectural appearance of the Tinchob Mosque, ensure the preservation of the monument, and extend its lifespan as a cultural heritage site.

Conclusion

As a result of historical, archival, bibliographic, and on-site research, it was established that the mosque underwent significant modifications during the Soviet period, associated with its conversion into a children's clinic. These interventions resulted in the partial loss of the original structures and decorative elements, but the main architectural forms, columns, and ceiling paintings remained in satisfactory condition.

On-site surveys using high-precision 3D laser scanning allowed for the creation of a detailed digital model of the building, ensuring accurate measurements and identifying structural deformations. Based on the collected data, a plan for restoring the original layout was developed and specific measures for the restoration and conservation of the monument were proposed.

The developed restoration project aims to scientifically restore the historical appearance of the Tinchob Mosque, preserving authentic elements and recreating lost parts in a manner similar to the original models. The planned activities include strengthening the supporting structures, restoring the plaster and decorative finishes, recreating the traditional roof, and landscaping the surrounding area.

The project will restore the Tinchob Mosque to its original architectural and artistic appearance, ensure its preservation for future generations, and restore its cultural and historical value as a significant element of Tashkent's urban development of the late 19th century.

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